

Conductance and viscosity studies of some univalent electrolytes in water, dimethyl sulfoxide and water + dimethyl sulfoxide mixtures at different temperatures

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Manuscript received 3 August 2001, revised 27 June 2002, accepted 12 July 2002

Conductance and viscosity of some univalent electrolytes have been measured in water, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and water + DMSO mixtures at different temperatures. The limiting molar conductance (Λ_0), limiting ionic conductances (λ_{i0}), Walden products ($\lambda_{i0}\eta_0$), solvated radii (r_i), viscosity A and B coefficients and ionic B_{\pm} values have been evaluated. These studies throw light on the effect of nature of electrolyte, solvent composition and temperature on the solvation behavior of ions in DMSO and DMSO + water mixtures.

The solvation behavior of ions in solution can be well understood in terms of ion-solvent, ion-ion and solvent-solvent interactions. Ion solvation is one of the most important factors that determines the rate and mechanism of various physiochemical processes occurring in solutions, involving ionic species as the intermediates^{1,2}.

In the present investigations, molar conductance and viscosity of sodium chloride, rubidium chloride, cesium chloride, sodium iodide, sodium tetraphenyl borate, tetrabutylammonium iodide (Bu_4NI) and tetrabutylammonium tetraphenyl boride (Bu_4NBPh_4) have been reported in water, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and water + DMSO mixtures containing 10, 25, 40, 55, 70, 85 mole % of water at 25, 35 and 45° in the concentration range ($1-300 \times 10^{-4}$) and ($5-400 \times 10^{-4}$) mole dm^{-3} , respectively. The conductance and viscosity measurements for Bu_4NBPh_4 could not be carried out beyond 45 mole % of DMSO because of the insoluble nature of the salt. The limiting ionic conductances,

the solvated radii, Walden products, viscosity A and B coefficients and the ionic B_{\pm} values have been evaluated and discussed in terms of ion-solvent interactions.

Results and Discussion

Conductance studies :

The conductance data have been analyzed using Shedlovsky's method³ with the help of least-squares program using computer to evaluate limiting molar conductance (Λ_0) values for above mentioned univalent electrolytes.

The physical constants like viscosity (η_0) and density (d) for DMSO and DMSO-water mixtures have been measured at 25, 35 and 45°. The observed and calculated values of various parameters, i.e. dielectric constant (D), viscosity (η_0), density (d) and Bjerrum critical distance (q) for the solvent systems at different temperatures are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Dielectric constant (D), viscosity (η_0), density (d) and the Bjerrum critical distance (q) for DMSO, water and DMSO + water mixtures at different temperatures

DMSO mole %	D			η_0 (cP)			d (g ml ⁻¹)			q (Å)		
	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°
100	46.4	44.7	43.3	1.991	1.663	1.411	1.0964	1.0858	1.0757	6.04	6.07	6.06
90	49.6	47.7	46.1	2.631	2.472	2.261	1.0987	1.0882	1.0780	5.65	5.68	5.70
75	54.4	52.3	50.4	3.592	3.348	3.129	1.0979	1.0873	1.0770	5.15	5.18	5.21
60	59.3	56.8	54.6	3.364	3.142	2.994	1.0988	1.0885	1.0784	4.73	4.77	4.81
45	64.1	61.4	58.8	2.514	2.329	2.172	1.0963	1.0847	1.0743	4.37	4.42	4.47
30	68.9	65.9	63.0	1.891	1.782	1.680	1.0877	1.0770	1.0681	4.07	4.11	4.17
15	73.7	70.5	67.3	1.372	1.280	1.170	1.0456	1.0432	1.0378	3.80	3.85	3.90
0	78.5	75.0	71.5	0.892	0.720	0.597	0.9971	0.9942	0.9902	3.57	3.61	3.67

Table 2. Limiting molar conductance ($\Lambda_0/S \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) values for some univalent electrolytes in DMSO, water and DMSO + water mixtures at different temperatures

Electrolyte	Temp. °C	Solvent (mole % DMSO)							
		100	90	75	60	45	30	15	0
Bu ₄ NBPh ₄	25	22.35	17.77	12.64	12.95	17.58	23.62	32.68	31.83
	35	28.22	19.54	14.42	15.85	20.77	26.93	38.16	49.28
	45	33.40	22.37	16.35	17.92	24.03	31.12	43.67	61.39
Bu ₄ NI	25	35.03	26.14	19.42	19.75	26.77	36.53	49.64	96.73
	35	42.87	28.86	21.50	22.93	30.57	40.29	56.18	118.32
	45	52.20	33.10	23.59	25.30	34.88	45.43	64.68	138.22
NaBPh ₄	25	24.49	18.46	13.21	14.34	19.68	26.80	37.46	65.65
	35	29.83	20.01	14.68	16.29	21.98	29.68	41.89	84.19
	45	36.78	23.05	16.06	17.61	24.23	32.13	46.04	104.82
NaI	25	36.86	27.47	20.08	21.16	28.64	39.71	54.42	130.45
	35	45.14	29.93	21.88	22.89	32.21	43.04	59.91	153.23
	45	54.21	33.58	23.12	24.33	35.68	46.44	67.05	181.65
NaCl	25	37.88	29.23	21.21	22.44	30.67	41.69	58.18	126.52
	35	47.28	31.65	23.43	24.27	35.31	45.75	64.62	153.89
	45	57.72	35.05	24.90	25.54	38.57	49.86	71.58	182.46
RbCl	25	41.11	31.42	23.81	24.36	31.36	46.76	65.24	154.87
	35	52.12	34.94	25.89	27.54	37.73	49.44	71.23	185.13
	45	62.17	38.93	28.19	30.32	42.87	54.55	77.24	216.42
CsCl	25	40.88	33.29	25.64	26.08	35.55	48.89	68.07	154.14
	35	54.45	37.46	28.00	29.70	41.80	53.08	76.53	184.10
	45	65.68	42.13	30.80	32.14	45.84	58.43	86.31	216.80

The observed limiting conductance (Λ_0) values for the univalent electrolytes are reported in Table 2. A reasonably good agreement between the experimental and literature values⁴ shows the accuracy of the measurements. As Bu₄NBPh₄ was not found soluble in mixtures having more than 45 mole % of DMSO in DMSO + water systems, Λ_0 values for Bu₄NBPh₄ above 45 mole % water (Table 2) have been calculated by using the additivity relation,

$$\Lambda_0(\text{Bu}_4\text{NBPh}_4) = \Lambda_0(\text{Bu}_4\text{NI}) + \Lambda_0(\text{NaBPh}_4) - \Lambda_0(\text{NaI})$$

The limiting equivalent conductance (Λ_0) for alkali metal salts in pure DMSO at 25° varies as follows : NaI < NaCl < RbCl ≤ CsCl. The Λ_0 values of the studied electrolytes have been resolved into λ_{\pm}^0 values on the basis of Bu₄NBPh₄ assumption⁵ and by using Kohlrausch's law of ionic mobility at infinite dilution over the whole solvent composition range. The calculated λ_{\pm}^0 values for Bu₄N⁺, Na⁺, Rb⁺, Cs⁺, Cl⁻, I⁻ and BPh₄⁻ are reported in Table 3.

The λ_{\pm}^0 values for alkali metal cations and anions at 25, 35 and 45° in DMSO and DMSO + water mixtures decrease as follows : Na⁺ < Rb⁺ < Cs⁺ and Ph₄B⁻ < I⁻ < Cl⁻. Similar behavior has been observed for alkali metal cations and anions in DMSO + dioxane mixtures⁶ at all the studied temperatures. A perusal of data (Table 3) shows that ionic conductance (λ_{\pm}^0) values for each studied ion is minimum at 25

mole % of water. Ionic conductance values increase with the increase of temperature in DMSO and DMSO + water solvent systems. The calculated ionic Walden product ($\lambda_{\pm}^0 \eta_0$) for various ions (Table 3), in general, increases with the increase of temperature but remains constant as the mole % of water is increased in DMSO + water mixtures.

The effective ionic radii (r_i) of ions in pure and mixed non-aqueous solvents have been calculated by Gill's empirical modification⁷ of Stokes law. The r_i values for various ions, i.e. Na⁺, Rb⁺, Cs⁺, Cl⁻, I⁻, Bu₄N⁺ and Ph₄B⁻ in water, DMSO and DMSO-water solvent system are reported in Table 4. It is seen that the r_i values for Na⁺, Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ in pure DMSO increase up to 75 mole % of DMSO, then decrease at 60 mole % and remain constant with further addition of water upto 15 mole % DMSO. A sharp decrease in r_i value is, however, observed when one moves from 15 mole % of DMSO to pure water for these cations. The increase in the r_i values for Na⁺, Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ from pure DMSO on addition of 25 mole % water shows the presence of intermolecular interaction which is broken by ion-solvent interaction. The almost constant r_i values for these ions from 60 to 15 mole % of DMSO, however, reflect that these cations interact preferentially with DMSO over this solvent composition range. Generally, cations like Na⁺, Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ are very much solvated by DMSO than water.

Table 3. Limiting ion conductance (λ_i^0) and Walden product ($\lambda_i^0\eta_0$) values for some univalent ions in DMSO, water and DMSO + water mixtures at 25°

Ion	Solvent (mole % DMSO)															
	100		90		75		60		45		30		15		0	
	λ_i^0	$\lambda_i^0\eta_0$	λ_i^0	$\lambda_i^0\eta_0$	λ_i^0	$\lambda_i^0\eta_0$	λ_i^0	$\lambda_i^0\eta_0$	λ_i^0	$\lambda_i^0\eta_0$	λ_i^0	$\lambda_i^0\eta_0$	λ_i^0	$\lambda_i^0\eta_0$	λ_i^0	$\lambda_i^0\eta_0$
Bu ₄ N ⁺	11.72	0.23	9.32	0.25	6.64	0.24	6.80	0.23	9.24	0.23	12.43	0.24	17.21	0.24	16.78	0.15
Na ⁺	13.55	0.27	10.65	0.28	7.30	0.26	8.31	0.28	11.11	0.28	15.61	0.30	21.99	0.30	50.50	0.45
Rb ⁺	16.78	0.33	12.84	0.34	9.90	0.36	10.23	0.34	11.80	0.36	20.68	0.39	29.05	0.40	77.85	0.70
Cs ⁺	16.55	0.33	14.71	0.39	11.73	0.42	11.95	0.40	15.99	0.40	22.81	0.43	31.88	0.44	78.12	0.70
BPh ₄ ⁻	10.63	0.21	8.45	0.22	6.00	0.22	6.15	0.21	8.34	0.23	11.19	0.21	15.47	0.21	15.05	0.13
I ⁻	23.31	0.46	16.82	0.44	12.78	0.46	12.95	0.44	17.53	0.44	24.10	0.46	32.43	0.44	79.95	0.71
Cl ⁻	24.33	0.48	18.58	0.49	13.91	0.50	14.18	0.48	19.56	0.49	26.08	0.49	36.19	0.50	76.02	0.68

Table 4. Solvated radii (r_i /nm) for some univalent ions in DMSO, water and DMSO + water mixtures at different temperatures

Ion	Temp. °C	Solvent (mole % DMSO)							
		100	90	75	60	45	30	15	0
Bu ₄ N ⁺	25	0.51	0.50	0.51	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.74
	35	0.49	0.49	0.49	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.63
	45	0.48	0.48	0.48	0.49	0.49	0.49	0.49	0.61
Na ⁺	25	0.46	0.46	0.48	0.47	0.47	0.46	0.46	0.38
	35	0.45	0.45	0.47	0.46	0.46	0.45	0.45	0.38
	45	0.45	0.46	0.49	0.46	0.45	0.46	0.46	0.37
Rb ⁺	25	0.40	0.41	0.42	0.40	0.39	0.39	0.39	0.31
	35	0.38	0.39	0.40	0.40	0.41	0.40	0.40	0.31
	45	0.39	0.39	0.40	0.38	0.38	0.39	0.39	0.31
Cs ⁺	25	0.38	0.39	0.41	0.38	0.38	0.37	0.38	0.31
	35	0.36	0.37	0.38	0.36	0.36	0.37	0.37	0.31
	45	0.36	0.38	0.39	0.35	0.36	0.37	0.36	0.31
BPh ₄ ⁻	25	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.80
	35	0.53	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.53	0.54	0.54	0.68
	45	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.52	0.66
I ⁻	25	0.34	0.35	0.35	0.36	0.36	0.36	0.37	0.31
	35	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.35	0.35	0.36	0.36	0.31
	45	0.33	0.33	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.35	0.31
Cl ⁻	25	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.31
	35	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.33	0.33	0.34	0.34	0.31
	45	0.31	0.32	0.32	0.33	0.32	0.33	0.33	0.31

The r_i values for Bu₄N⁺, Ph₄B⁻, I⁻ and Cl⁻ ions either remain constant or show slight increase up to 15 mole % of water. However, a sharp increase in r_i values for Bu₄N⁺ and Ph₄B⁻ and decrease for I⁻ and Cl⁻ is observed from 15 mole % of DMSO to pure water which can be attributed to the solvophobic solvation effect of water, and further large decrease in r_i values for I⁻, Cl⁻, Na⁺, Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ ions from 85 mole % water to pure water can be accounted for the strong hydration of these ions by water, respectively. A slight decrease and constancy in the r_i values for Na⁺, Rb⁺ and

Cs⁺ above 25 mole % of water can be attributed to the structural consequences of intermolecular interactions, as DMSO shows much stronger electron pair donating (EPD) ability than water. Moreover, it is evident that r_i values of Na⁺, Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ ions show non-linear dependence on water concentration showing that these cations are preferentially solvated by DMSO in water-rich region and are preferentially hydrated by water in DMSO-rich region. Syal *et al.*⁵ observed that Li⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺ ions experience stronger electrostatic ion-solvent interactions with DMSO in AN +

DMSO mixtures, having strong preferential solvation by DMSO over the whole solvent composition, whereas in Ac + DMSO⁸ solvent systems, these authors suggested that Li⁺ and Na⁺ ions show strong solvation by DMSO in Ac-rich region and by Ac in DMSO-rich region. These authors also reported the non-solvation behavior of Bu₄N⁺, Ph₄B⁻, Cl⁻ and Br⁻ ions in AN + DMSO and DMSO + Ac mixtures.

Table 4 reveals that there is no effect of temperature on the r_i values for Na⁺, Rb⁺, Cs⁺, I⁻ and Cl⁻. However, in all solvent compositions, r_i values for BPh₄⁻ and Bu₄N⁺ ions decrease with the increase of temperature in pure water but there is no appreciable effect of temperature on r_i values in DMSO and DMSO + water solvent system. Similar effect of temperature on r_i values of alkali metal, Ag⁺, Cu⁺, tetraalkylammonium cations and anions has been reported earlier⁵.

Syal *et al.*⁹ in their studies on DMSO + dioxane reported that r_i values for Li⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺ ions vary linearly with the decrease of DMSO content in DMSO + dioxane mixtures, thereby, indicating that these ions show no change in preferential solvation from DMSO to DMSO + dioxane mixtures though these ions are known to be strongly solvated in DMSO and poorly solvated in dioxane.

The above findings show that solvation behavior of Na⁺, Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ ions in DMSO + water mixture is quite simi-

lar to that observed in AN + DMF¹⁰, Ac + DMF¹¹ and AN + DMSO⁵ but is different from that observed in DMSO + dioxane⁹.

Viscosity studies :

The entire viscosity data have been analyzed with the help of Jones-Dole equation¹² to get the values of viscosity A and B coefficients for all the electrolytes in DMSO, water and DMSO-water mixtures at different temperatures by least-square fitting method with the help of computer and only B -values are reported in Table 5 at 25, 35 and 45°. Both these coefficients have been found to be positive and large, which is a common feature observed in most of the non-aqueous solvents¹³. The positive B -values indicate that any structure-breaking tendencies by these electrolytes is relatively less important in DMSO-water solvent systems than in structured solvent system like MeOH-water¹⁴. The A -coefficients of electrolytes obtained from the plots are found in good agreement with the corresponding A_{77} coefficients calculated theoretically using Falkenhagen-Vernon equation¹⁵.

To analyze the ion-solvent interactions, the B -values of the electrolytes have been resolved into ionic contribution, i.e. B_{\pm} values based upon Bu₄NBPh₄ assumption as suggested by Gill and Sharma¹⁶. From the calculated B_{\pm} values of Bu₄N⁺ and Ph₄B⁻ ions and B values of other electrolytes from Table 5, B_{\pm} values for all other ions, i.e. Na⁺, Rb⁺,

Table 5. Experimentally determined viscosity B (dm³ mol⁻¹) coefficients for some univalent electrolytes in DMSO, water and DMSO + water mixtures at different temperatures

Electrolyte	Temp. °C	Solvent (mole % DMSO)							
		100	90	75	60	45	30	15	0
Bu ₄ NBPh ₄	25	1.43	1.57	1.63	1.64	1.75	1.70	1.76	1.74
	35	1.44	1.58	1.64	1.65	1.76	1.72	1.76	1.76
	45	1.45	1.59	1.65	1.65	1.77	1.73	1.78	1.77
Bu ₄ NI	25	0.91	1.15	1.26	1.26	1.24	1.25	1.26	1.26
	35	0.92	1.16	1.27	1.27	1.25	1.26	1.26	1.27
	45	0.92	1.16	1.27	1.27	1.25	1.26	1.27	1.27
NaBPh ₄	25	1.39	1.41	1.44	1.45	1.45	1.45	1.50	1.48
	35	1.40	1.42	1.45	1.46	1.46	1.47	1.50	1.49
	45	1.41	1.43	1.46	1.47	1.47	1.48	1.51	1.50
NaI	25	1.06	1.07	1.09	1.10	1.09	1.10	1.10	1.10
	35	1.06	1.07	1.09	1.10	1.09	1.10	1.10	1.10
	45	1.06	1.07	1.09	1.10	1.09	1.10	1.10	1.10
NaCl	25	0.94	0.95	0.96	0.97	0.98	0.99	1.00	1.01
	35	0.95	0.95	0.97	0.97	0.99	0.99	1.00	1.01
	45	0.95	0.96	0.97	0.98	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.01
RbCl	25	0.91	0.92	0.93	0.94	0.95	0.95	0.97	0.97
	35	0.92	0.93	0.94	0.94	0.95	0.95	0.97	0.97
	45	0.92	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.95	0.95	0.97	0.97
CsCl	25	0.88	0.89	0.90	0.91	0.92	0.93	0.94	0.95
	35	0.89	0.90	0.91	0.91	0.92	0.93	0.94	0.95
	45	0.90	0.90	0.91	0.91	0.93	0.93	0.94	0.96

Table 6. Experimentally determined viscosity B_{\pm} ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) coefficients for some univalent ions in DMSO, water and DMSO + water mixtures at different temperatures

Ion.	Temp. °C	Solvent (mole % DMSO)							
		100	90	75	60	45	30	15	0
Bu_4N^+	25	0.64	0.71	0.73	0.74	0.79	0.76	0.79	0.78
	35	0.65	0.71	0.74	0.74	0.79	0.77	0.79	0.79
	45	0.65	0.71	0.74	0.74	0.80	0.78	0.80	0.80
Na^+	25	0.79	0.63	0.56	0.58	0.64	0.61	0.63	0.62
	35	0.79	0.62	0.56	0.57	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63
	45	0.79	0.62	0.56	0.57	0.64	0.63	0.63	0.63
Rb^+	25	0.76	0.60	0.53	0.55	0.61	0.57	0.60	0.58
	35	0.76	0.60	0.53	0.54	0.59	0.60	0.60	0.59
	45	0.76	0.60	0.53	0.53	0.61	0.57	0.60	0.59
Cs^+	25	0.73	0.56	0.50	0.52	0.58	0.55	0.57	0.56
	35	0.73	0.57	0.50	0.51	0.56	0.57	0.57	0.57
	45	0.74	0.56	0.50	0.50	0.59	0.56	0.57	0.58
BPh_4^-	25	0.79	0.86	0.90	0.90	0.96	0.94	0.97	0.96
	35	0.79	0.87	0.90	0.91	0.97	0.95	0.97	0.97
	45	0.80	0.88	0.91	0.91	0.97	0.95	0.98	0.97
I^-	25	0.27	0.44	0.52	0.52	0.45	0.49	0.47	0.48
	35	0.27	0.45	0.53	0.53	0.46	0.49	0.47	0.47
	45	0.27	0.45	0.53	0.53	0.48	0.48	0.47	0.47
Cl^-	25	0.15	0.32	0.40	0.39	0.34	0.38	0.37	0.39
	35	0.16	0.33	0.41	0.40	0.36	0.38	0.37	0.38
	45	0.16	0.34	0.41	0.41	0.40	0.37	0.37	0.38

Cs^+ , I^- and Cl^- have been calculated on the basis of additivity relationship and are reported in Table 6 at all the studied temperatures. The B_{\pm} values of univalent cations and anions in DMSO vary in the order: $\text{Na}^+ > \text{Rb}^+ > \text{Cs}^+$ and $\text{I}^- > \text{Cl}^-$, which clearly indicates the dependence of B_{\pm} values for these ions on the size of univalent ions.

Table 6 reveals that B_{\pm} values for Na^+ , Rb^+ and Cs^+ decrease from pure DMSO up to 75 mole % of DMSO, and then increase, and remain almost constant with the further addition of water to DMSO up to pure water. This non-linear variation of B_{\pm} alkali metal ions with solvent composition can be inferred that these ions are preferentially solvated by DMSO in water-rich region and are hydrated by water in DMSO-rich region. Also, this non-linear variation shows the presence of ion-solvent interaction being minimum at ~75 mole % of DMSO. This has been further supported by the ionic conductance values or radii values given earlier. Thus, the results obtained from viscosity measurements for these electrolytes in DMSO, water and DMSO + water mixtures are found to be compatible with those obtained from conductance studies.

Experimental

Conductance was measured at 1 kHz frequency using a NDC-732 conductivity (accuracy of $\pm 0.2\%$). Viscosity was measured with an Ubbelohde suspended bulb level viscometer. The kinematic viscosity (cst) was converted to absolute viscosity using density values measured for each solute by two sealable pycnometers of different capacities (20 and 25 ml) with the reproducibility of $\pm 0.001 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, and within accuracy of $\pm 0.2\%$.

The conductivity meter, pycnometer and viscometer were periodically calibrated using triple-distilled water and other purified solvents. DMSO and water were purified as per reported methods⁵. Purity of the solvents was checked by comparing their viscosity and density values with the literature values⁵. The salts were used as such after drying in vacuum oven. The details of conductance cell and experimental procedure for conductance and viscosity measurements were the same as reported earlier⁵⁻⁸.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (V.K.S. and S.C.) thank U.G.C., New

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Delhi, for the grant of major research project and research associateship respectively.

References

1. A. J. Parker, *Quart. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **16**, 163; *Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **69**, 1; *Proc. R. Aust. Chem. Inst.*, 1972, **39**, 163; *Search*, 1973, **4**, 426.
2. C. V. Jettisoning, D. Nikola and S. Mentus, *Phys. Chem.*, 1999, **1**, 5157.
3. R. M. Fuoss and T. Shedlovsky, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 1496.
4. M. S. Chauhan, K. Sharma and S. Chauhan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1082.
5. V. K. Syal, S. Chauhan and M. S. Chauhan, *Z. Phys. Chem. (N.F.)*, 1988, **159**, 49.
6. V. K. Syal, P. Bisht and P. C. Ranowt, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1991, **56**, 1813.
7. D. S. Gill, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1977, **22**, 491; 1979, **24**, 701.
8. V. K. Syal, S. Chauhan, A. Katoch and M. S. Chauhan, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1991, **56**, 1803.
9. V. K. Syal, P. Bisht and M. S. Chauhan, *Proct. Natl. Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1991, **61**, 561.
10. D. S. Gill and J. S. Cheema, *Z. Phys. Chem. (N.F.)*, 1983, **134**, 205.
11. D. S. Gill, A. N. Sharma and H. Schneider, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1982, 465.
12. G. Jones and M. Dole, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950.
13. S. Chauhan, Ph.D. Thesis, H. P. University, India, 1988.
14. N. C. Das and P. B. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 824, 1098.
15. H. Falkenhagen and E. L. Vernon, *Phil. Mag.*, 1932, **14**, 537.
16. D. S. Gill and A. N. Sharma, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1982, 475.
17. R. Palepu, R. Johnson and W. Rolls, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1985, **30**, 69.